

Combining Thermochemical and Phase Change Materials for Thermal Energy Storage: the Echo Project

Laura Vallese^{a,b,#}, Giulia Lombardo^{a,b}, Davide Menegazzo^a, Giovanni Ferrarini^a, Mauro Scattolini^a, Sergio Bobbo^a, Laura Fedele^a

^a Construction Technologies Institute, National Research Council (CNR), Padova, Italy

^b Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Padova, Padova, Italy

#Corresponding Author: laura.vallese@phd.unipd.it

Abstract

Buildings are responsible for 40% of the total energy consumption in Europe, making this sector crucial to achieve the decarbonization goals set by the European Green Deal. Against this background, thermal energy storage (TES) plays a pivotal role in reducing the mismatch between energy supply and demand, along with favoring the integration of renewable energy sources. While sensible heat storage is a well-established technology, research is focusing on latent heat and thermochemical systems, which are characterized by higher energy density.

In this context, the Horizon Europe project ECHO is going to combine innovative phase change materials (PCMs) with a composite vermiculite-CaCl₂ thermochemical material (TCM), with the aim to develop an efficient, compact, and modular TES system. A heat pump will charge a closed TCM reactor at 80 °C, thus coupling the electricity and heating sector by converting the excess photovoltaic power to stored heat. The reactor will be insulated through polyurethane PCM foams. A paraffin-based PCM storage will be used as a buffer during periods of high heating demand and as a source for humidification of the air during the discharging phase. Additionally, a cold storage system exploiting a eutectic PCM solution of Na₂CO₃ is planned for high cooling loads. Three test cases are going to be installed in Italy, Serbia, and Belgium, to assess the performance of the systems in different conditions, demonstrating its flexibility and adaptability to both stand-alone and grid-connected buildings.

1. introduction

1.1. Thermal energy storage

The objectives of the European Green Deal require to achieve net zero greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 2050 [1]. Renewable energy sources (RES) are the most promising alternatives to fossil fuels, in the perspective of mitigating climate change and reaching the set goals. However, their intrinsic intermittency requires adopting energy storage solutions [2]. Among the different categories, thermal energy storage (TES) is the most suitable for application in buildings, which in Europe account for 40 % of the final energy consumption. Decarbonizing this sector is of great importance, considering that

fossil fuels supply two thirds of the energy for space heating and cooling [3]. The main advantages of TES systems include the reduction of the mismatch between energy demand and supply [4] any improvements in thermal energy management practices can significantly benefit the society. One key function in thermal energy management is thermal energy storage (TES, and the opportunity to integrate RES through sector coupling, decarbonizing both the heating and electricity sector [5].

TES systems can be classified according to the application, the temperature range or, most commonly, the technology. Sensible heat storage is the simplest and most mature TES technology, involving the increase or decrease of temperature of the storage medium, usually water [6]. Latent heat storage is based on the phase transition of specific materials, offering high energy density with a reduced operating temperature range [7]. Thermochemical energy storage takes advantage of reversible chemical reactions, usually consisting of sorption. During charging, the two components involved in the reaction are separated by exploiting an external heat source. They can be stored until when heat is discharged through an exothermic reaction. This technology can achieve values of energy storage density 5-10 times higher than sensible and latent heat storage systems [8].

2. The echo project

2.1. Description and aim

The Horizon EU project ECHO (Efficient Compact Modular Thermal Energy Storage) contributes to research on thermal energy storage by designing and developing an innovative system, intended for application in buildings [10]. The proposed TES configuration integrates both PCMs and a TCM for supplying heating, cooling and domestic hot water to the user. The final aim is to store thermal energy in an efficient way, allowing the integration of RES and providing load shifting. The project is well described and synthesized through the following five objectives:

1. Definition of the fundamental parameters for the design of the system, thus considering different energy scenarios, energy demands and possibilities of connection to the electricity grid.
2. Selection of the most suitable materials, which are the core of the system and include a TCM and two different kinds of PCMs.
3. Construction of the complete plug&play system, whose main strengths are

modularity, flexibility and digital control.

4. Demonstration of the benefits of innovative TES systems, which represent an important opportunity to the transition towards more efficient, sustainable and adaptive heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems.
5. Raise awareness on affordability, supply security and grid stability of adopting innovative TES solutions for buildings.

The core of the system is the TCM reactor, which is directly charged by a heat pump specifically designed for this application (Figure 1). This allows to integrate RES and to provide load shifting, by converting the excess photovoltaic power to stored heat. During the charging phase, air at around 80 °C flows through the reactor containing a composite of vermiculite and CaCl₂, arranged in drawers. On the other hand, discharging of the stored thermal energy involves the hydration of the composite TCM through humid air. For this purpose, an ultrasonic humidifier will be employed. To meet high cooling requirements in summer, an additional unit consisting of a cold PCM storage is added to the system. PCMs are also going to be used for insulation of the TCM reactor and to fill a buffer tank functioning as energy source for water evaporation.

Figure 1. Schematic overview of the TES system.

2.2. Work packages

ECHO involves seventeen partners from Italy, Spain, Turkey, UK, Serbia, Belgium and Romania, and is organized in eight work packages (WPs).

Project management and coordination are addressed by WP1, whose main purposes are to monitor and supervise the progression in time of the project, to take care of the administrative and financial activities and to manage the data related to the project and the achieved results.

WP2 focusses on the conceptualization and design of the TES system, aiming to assess its impact through agent-based simulations, called ECHOTSS (ECHO transaction simulation system). Scenarios involving different climates and energy demands will be simulated. The work is set in the European context through a comprehensive analysis of the state of the art on TES systems, the creation of a database including the available technologies and a SWOT analysis. The WP is also in charge for the definition of design and control indicators and for assessing the risks related to the three demo sites.

The selection of the materials and the related design of the system is carried out in WP3. A significant effort is dedicated to the characterization and fabrication of a suitable TCM, necessary for properly designing the reactor at the heart of the TES system. Proper PCMs are selected to fulfil the buffer and the cold storage requirements, respectively. Potential risks, such as corrosion, are analyzed and suitable solutions to contrast them are found.

The main objective of WP4 is the construction of a lab-scale prototype of the system. This is preceded by a preliminary design and the creation of a numerical model to support the control of the system. The prototype will be monitored in different conditions, assessing its energy performance and optimizing it.

The control system is being developed in WP5, including the design and manufacturing of the hardware, the creation of the control algorithm and the application of the control system to the demo sites.

The demonstration of three test cases is on charge of WP6. The ECHO TES system will be monitored in different locations and conditions, considering the performance, adaptability and reliability. Moreover, tests for the implementation of ECHOTSS will be conducted.

WP7 focusses on the evaluation of the potential reduction of the environmental impact

and of the peak load minimizing costs through the life cycle assessment (LCA) and LCCA respectively. Environmental and risk assessment will be carried out, together with the definition of actions to favor market exploitation and planning.

Finally, WP8 involves dissemination, communication, and networking and training activities.

3. Materials for thermal energy storage

3.1. Thermochemical materials

Thermochemical materials are the most promising mediums for energy storage, thanks to their high theoretical energy density. These materials undergo a reversible chemical reaction. The charging phase consists of the decomposition or desorption of the material, which are endothermic processes, while the discharging process is exothermic [11]. The main features sought for storage applications are a large porous surface area, good mechanical properties and low charging temperature [12]. Among the available options, salt hydrates are particularly suitable for providing space heating and DHW in buildings, thanks to their low operating temperature and relatively low cost [13]. However, they are usually incorporated in composite materials to improve their stability and heat and mass transfer. The materials functioning as matrixes are chosen among adsorbents, like zeolite or silica gel, or for their porosity, like natural rocks, or for their high thermal conductivity, such as expanded graphite [14].

In the context of the ECHO project, the partners involved in WP3 have selected a composite of CaCl_2 and vermiculite. CaCl_2 is a non-toxic hygroscopic salt which can adsorb up to six water molecules. Its main advantages include a high sorption rate, chemical stability and low corrosiveness. Vermiculite is interesting as host matrix thanks to its low cost, high porosity, durability and low weight [15]. According to Zhang et al., vacuum impregnation is the most promising method for synthesizing this composite TCM. The benefits compared to other methods include higher salt infiltration and higher volumetric energy density (2.05 GJ m^{-3}) [16]. The composite TCM was characterized through the scanning electron microscope (SEM) analysis, to evaluate its morphology and microstructure. The content of salt was evaluated through an inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometer (ICP-OES), and an energy storage density analysis was carried out. Further experimentation on the cyclability of the material is foreseen,

as well as a more detailed characterization in the context of the prototype and of the demo sites.

3.2. Phase change materials

Phase change materials can store large amounts of heat during phase change, at approximately constant temperature. When choosing a PCM, the melting point is one of the most important features to take into account, and it should be compatible with the operating range [17]. Other required properties are high latent heat and thermal conductivity, minimum subcooling during melting and chemical stability [18] but also within architects and engineers. Many publications have appeared, and several books, but the information is disseminated and not very much organised. This paper shows a review of the latest publications on the use of phase change materials (PCM). PCMs can be classified according to their operating temperature or the type of phase transition. Solid-liquid PCMs are the most widespread and are further divided into inorganic and organic substances [7]. The advantages of organic PCMs include high stability, non-corrosiveness and high latent heat of fusion. On the other hand, inorganic compounds are characterized by high phase change enthalpy and thermal conductivity. Eutectic PCMs combine two or more organic or inorganic materials, which change phase at the same moment [17].

For the ECHO project, two different PCMs have been selected so far.

A paraffin-based PCM (Table 1) was proven to be the best option for the buffer storage, to be operated between 27 and 35 °C.

Table 1 Properties of the selected paraffin-based PCM A32, according to the manufacturer [19].

	Phase change T (°C)	Density (kg /m ³)	Latent Heat Capacity (kJ/kg)	Volumetric Heat capacity (MJ/m ³)	Specific Heat capacity (kJ/KgK)	Thermal conductivity (W/mK)	Maximum operating temperature (°C)
A32 PCM	32	845	120	101	2.2	0.121	200

The choice was made after comparing it to a salt hydrate based on sodium sulphate, which during experimental tests showed stability issues and subcooling around 27 °C. Furthermore, the salt hydrate is subject to the risk of decomposition at temperatures

higher than 60 °C, not compatible with temperatures that can be reached in the system. The average latent heat and subcooling of the two PCMs were characterized through differential scanning calorimetry (DSC).

For the cold storage application, the phase change temperature is required to be below 0 °C. The selection of the most suitable PCM was based on the analysis of its thermophysical properties, including the phase change temperature, the specific heat capacity and the latent heat. The last two properties were measured through DSC at the Construction Technologies Institute of the National Research Council of Italy (ITC-CNR). The eutectic mixture identified as most suitable candidate for this application is sodium carbonate and water ($\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$), being characterized by a higher latent heat compared to another water-salt solution.

Along with the characterization of the composite TCM, also the thermophysical properties of these PCMs will be evaluated more in depth during the operation of the prototype and of the demo sites.

4. Conclusions

TES is a key technology to reach the ambitious goals set by the European Green Deal. In this framework, the Horizon EU ECHO project advances research in TES by developing an innovative system integrating PCMs and a TCM to support buildings' heating, cooling, and domestic hot water needs. The project's objectives emphasize designing a modular, flexible, and digitally controlled system, which can demonstrate the advantages of TES in improving the efficiency, sustainability, and adaptability of HVAC systems.

Materials selection is crucial when implementing new TES technologies. In the ECHO project, the chosen materials include a composite of CaCl_2 and vermiculite for the TCM reactor, a paraffin-based PCM for the buffer storage, and a eutectic mixture of Na_2CO_3 and H_2O for the cold accumulator. The chosen materials exhibit favorable properties such as high energy density, stability, and compatibility with the operating conditions. This project's innovations highlight the potential of TES systems to contribute significantly to the energy transition, favoring the spread of RES and increasing efficiency in buildings.

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